

Caspase 7 is activated in severe Crohn's Disease.

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We utilized whole transcriptome technologies to profile expression of the caspase family of enzymes that functions in apoptosis and inflammation in the hematopoietic compartment of humans with the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease. Caspase-1, caspase-4, caspase-5, and caspase-7 were each expressed in abundant quantity in active disease in the hematopoietic system of patients with Crohn's Disease, but only caspase-7 was inducibly activated in the blood during periods of active disease. Caspase-7 was co-regulated with phospholipid signaling components *PLSCR1* and *ITPRIPL2*, alpha kinase 1, *TNFSF10*, Bcl-3 and Bcl-10 and the necroptotic kinase *MLKL*, as well as IL-15 with the alpha subunit of the IL-15 receptor. IL-15 activation in active but not inactive disease together suggested an inflammatory function for caspase-7 and IL-15 in humans with Crohn's Disease. The data establish specific caspase and interleukin induction concomitant with disease exacerbation in humans with Crohn's Disease.

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